

The Prevalence of Nepotism in the Entertainment Industry

Alyssa Solomon

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Literature Review

Defining Nepotism

Nepotism was first coined in the late 14th century to describe the favouritism and unfair employment advantages received by Pope Calixtus III's nephews (White 109). The term nepotism originates from the Latin words 'nepos' meaning nephew and 'nepotis' meaning grandson (Safina 631), but the current definition encompasses the preferential selection of any family member (Padgett et al. 283). While for most academic purposes, the definition is sufficient for consistency between studies, it does leave room for differing interpretations that complicate efforts to measure nepotism. For example, some sources, such as Burhan et al., interpret this definition to mean simply hiring a relative is not necessarily nepotism if there are no candidates more qualified than the relative. Yet, this specificity often doesn't align with outside perspectives or general notions of nepotism that are purely dependent on family ties.

Public Perception

While scholars define nepotism narrowly, public perception often diverges. Two different studies focused on the general population's perception found that people tend to view nepotism beneficiaries negatively regardless of how qualified they are (Padgett et al. 295; Burhan et al. 40). These negative stigmas include perceptions of less competence, less effort, and less ability overall to perform the job than their non-related, but equally qualified counterparts. The explanation given by researchers, such as Burhan et al., is that the dislike of nepotism isn't rooted in meritocratic ideals, rather it reflects a procedural fairness perspective (Burhan et al. 37). A procedural fairness perspective critiques how meritocracy is focused on the fairness of the outcome and often neglects to acknowledge the unequal means that led to those results. For example, if the employer was previously biased toward one of the candidates and that individual then receives the position, it

can lead outsiders to believe that it was a false hiring process and therefore the other candidates did not truly have an opportunity regardless of their own qualifications (Padgett et al. 296). A procedural fairness perspective could further rationalise that if the hiring process was done for the sole purpose of hiring a family member, then the qualification requirements for the job posting could be altered to best suit that family member thus undermining a meritocracy in the first place (Burhan et al. 37). In recent years, there has been a spotlight on this critique of nepotism in mainstream media, especially within celebrity culture as the term ‘nepo baby’ rose in popularity. People online began expressing their surprise in discovering that many celebrities have parents who were previously established in the industry. As well, a portion of this group expressed their dissatisfaction in these discoveries due to the presumption of favouritism and unfair opportunities commonly associated with nepotism (Padgett et al. 295; Burhan et al. 40). Public opinion appears rather divided as some argue in defense of nepotism beneficiaries, considering they did not choose to be born into the entertainment industry and rather simply use their position to their benefit. While media discourse tends to be centered on individuals, the scholarly discussion examines the concept of nepotism as a whole.

Categorizing Nepotism

Defenses of nepotism often arise from differentiating between direct and indirect forms of nepotism (Gorji et al. 1). While direct forms neglect to consider ability and competence, indirect forms only occur once an individual has demonstrated adequate ability and competence first, thus, hypothetically, the individual has worked for the role (Gorji et al. 1; Burhan et al. 35). Some scholars make this distinction to criticize the overt, clearly unjust forms of nepotism while justifying less extreme cases with merit. A cultural frame analysis of over 300 articles found that “most commonly, nepotism among celebrity children is rendered defensible through allusions to

hard work” (Foster, Maroto n.p.). Some researchers critique this narrative as “hiding structural inequalities and the insidiousness of privilege from view” (Foster, Maroto n.p.), since, for an outsider entering the entertainment industry, having ability and competence is the bare minimum and they must also work to develop their own network and reputation without inherited assistance. While the boundary between earned success and inherited advantage is difficult to differentiate on an individual basis, the distinction between nepotism types obfuscates from the much larger distinction between those born with the privilege and those born without. Justifying indirect nepotism beneficiaries because they must prove their competency first neglects to acknowledge critiques of nepotism from the procedural fairness perspective, that those with familial ties have more and better opportunities to demonstrate their competency in the first place through their families’ connections.

Film Industry Structure

In show business, networking and connections are vital to employment: “the majority of those working in the film industry, as well those attempting to gain access to it, hear of and secure work through a... personal contact who performs functions such as providing recommendations” (Blair 152). In a case study of a production, 56% of the employees cited a friend or family member for how they entered the film industry (Blair 159). While a case study does not represent the industry in its entirety, it provides insight into the hiring mechanisms that may be present across similar network-based productions. Nepotism prospers in this structure where “getting cast and advancing one’s career in the Hollywood movie industry ... depend[s] heavily on the depth and breadth of one’s interpersonal networks” (Gorji et al. 4). Therefore, pre-established ties create a form of privilege that is disproportionately advantageous for nepotism beneficiaries, regardless of their own merit. This can be further seen in the fact that nepotism “is most prevalent at the highest

levels of the income hierarchy” (Gorji et al. 1) displaying how nepotism is interconnected with systemic wealth disparity. Measuring exactly how prevalent nepotism is within the most successful actors of the film industry, who are at high levels of the income hierarchy, can explore this concept in further detail.

Gap

The topic of nepotism is a source of debate among scholars as well as the general public, with some emphasizing individualism narratives of merit and hard work and others refuting that nepotism is a more societally embedded form of inherited privilege. Despite extensive analysis on classifications, general perceptions, and cultural narratives of nepotism, there is comparatively little insight into its overall prevalence. This imbalance suggests that scholarly attention has prioritized interpretive analysis over quantitative assessment. Additionally, there is a lack of studies comparing nepotism in the entertainment industry over time which could potentially provide an insight into the recent mainstream interest of ‘nepo babies’. Considering that “the film industry and its practices shift over time and should be re-evaluated empirically” (Dadlani et al. 20), comparisons across time periods could provide useful data for analyzing these changes. This study aims to address this gap by contributing quantitative evidence to a topic that is typically discussed in qualitative or perceptual terms.

Research Focus

In a generalized sense, demographic data of successful Hollywood actors could bring awareness to issues of inequality within the film industry or demonstrate that public dissatisfaction in the appearance of nepotism is rooted in more complex social issues than objective measurements. The void of quantitative studies comparing those who benefit from nepotism to

those who don't prompts the question: how does the ratio of actors with familial ties to established entertainment professionals to those without ties cast in leading roles of top-grossing films in 1980–1990 compare to the latest decade?

Methodology

This study aims to compare the prevalence of clear nepotism in the entertainment industry during the '80s to the last 10 years. As consistent with similar studies (Gorji et al. 5; Dadlani et al. 1), the data collected will be from the International Movie Database (IMDb) for the following reasons. First, the database contains all the information directly relevant to the research question. Each movie has the amount of money grossed, the year it was released, and the cast in order of the movie's credits. Second, each actor's profile on the database provides a list of relatives. If the relative has no role in the creation of a movie or television series, they will have no profile on the database. Third, IMDb is one of the most reputable and expansive databases for this area, with all information being accurately gathered, so it is the most trusted site with which to conduct this research.

The leads in top grossing films were chosen as the best measurement of success for this study because it can be assumed for most cases that a high-level involvement in a popular film correlates with fame. Other options such as awards or financial earnings were considered but ultimately discarded since deciding which awards to consider would either limit the sample size or create a disjointed sample of varying qualifications, and public actor's salaries are often unreliable or unavailable. Top-grossing films were chosen because they are representative of both popularity and financial success subsequently for the lead actors as well.

Selection of Films

Since this study aims to compare two different decades, there will be two different groups of films being analyzed. Group 1 will consist of movies that were released between the years of 1980 and 1990. These dates were chosen due to the shift from the studio-based entertainment industry to the contemporary network-based industry around 1960 to 1975 (Blair 151; Gorji et al. 5). The '80s, being the first decade to completely adopt the new system, was chosen as to not introduce the variable of differing industry structures. Additionally, choosing 1980 to 1990 ensures that the majority of familial information is available compared to previous decades where there is a higher chance of familial ties not being recorded.

Group 2 will consist of movies that were released between the years of 2014 and 2024. This 10-year period was chosen due to being the most recent complete decade at the start of the research process, therefore the most relevant to the recent spotlight on nepotism and for analysis on the current climate.

The lists used for both groups was created from IMDb's list of the top grossing films worldwide of all time ("Top Lifetime Grosses"). This list uses USD currency and does not adjust for inflation. This will not have an impact on the study considering the two separate groups for each time period. Re-releases, special editions, and international reissues are included since the list considers lifetime grosses, but this still portrays an accurate collection of the most successful films despite this. Only the top 100 movies between the selected years will be used from this list. These movies can be found listed in the appendix.

Sampling

The first five actors of each film were selected to balance between movies such as *Avengers: Endgame* that has arguably over ten main actors and movies such as *Indiana Jones and*

the Last Crusade that is commonly thought of to have only two main actors. Additionally, five provides an appropriate amount of data since if one actor were to appear multiple times in the same group, their data would not be counted. For example, Mark Hamill, Harrison Ford, and Carrie Fisher are only counted once in Group 1 for *Star Wars: Episode V - The Empire Strikes Back* and are not inputted a second time for *Star Wars: Episode VI - Return of the Jedi*. This is necessary so individuals do not disproportionately influence the dataset because the aim of the study is to analyze the ratio of nepotistic actors to non-nepotistic actors and not individual popularity. Actors who appear in both Group 1 and Group 2 will be counted in each group once, however. For instance, Sigourney Weaver appears in both *Ghostbusters* 1984 and *Avatar: The Way of Water* 2022 and is counted for both movies. Since each decade is analyzed independently from the other, an actor's prominence in one does not impact the other. Counting actors separately in each decade reflects the entertainment industry's decision to continue to provide leading roles in the context of different hiring trends.

Ethical Considerations

This study uses publicly available information accessible on IMDb and does not collect or disclose any private, personal, or identifiable information. Actors' nepotistic status was determined with verifiable evidence of familial ties to established entertainment professionals from reputable publications and/or authenticated biographies. All actors were categorized under the same systematic pre-defined criteria, and no speculative claims were factored into the analysis. All information gathered is available in the appendix for complete transparency.

Coding Actors

After an actor has met the qualifications to be considered, their name and gender were recorded. Gender was a factor recorded due to the nature of the network-based industry which can lead to gender inequalities (Lutter 346). In a similar study, women were shown to benefit more from nepotism and use it to overcome adversity in the workplace, especially when considering social capital and sponsorship from family members (Gorji et al. 9). Since “women tend to remain on the periphery of networks unless they can create ties with key players” (Dadlani et al. 9), women who are born with pre-established ties to key players are predicted to find easier success. In line with this study’s focus, analyzing whether the ratio of nepotism prevalence differs between genders could present an insight into further inequalities.

Following this, the actor’s profile would be analyzed under the section “Personal details”. Only the categories “Parents” and “Relatives” would contribute to the actor’s nepotism status considering that spouses and children do not fall under the category of nepotism. Actors would either be coded with a 0, indicating no nepotism status, or a 1, indicating nepotism status. If none of the names listed under these categories had profiles on IMDb, the actor would receive a 0. If a relative or parent did have profiles, then their profiles would be compared with that of the actor’s. To receive a 1, the relative or parent must have had a role, e.g., produced, written, directed, acted, etc., in a production before the date of the actor’s first involvement in a production. For example, Robert Downey Jr.’s first involvement in a film or television series was acting in *Pound* in 1970. His father, Robert Downey Sr.’s first involvement was in 1961, which predates the start of Robert Downey Jr.’s career meaning he is coded as a 1. However, for example, Zoe Saldña is coded as a 0 because her first appearance predates that of her sister’s. She was in *Law and Order* in 1999 while her sister, Cisely Saldña’s, first production was in 2009. This was to ensure that actors were not marked as nepotism benefactors if their relative was possibly benefiting from them. This does

not account for whether the relative's productions were successful as it would still be coded as nepotism due to the benefactor still having the opportunity for insider knowledge and support from within the industry. There were a few exceptions, such as game show contestants, which were not counted due to not being relevant enough to the acting industry.

Even though all actors with nepotism status would receive a 1, multiple nepotistic relatives would be recorded. This is to differentiate between isolated cases of individuals using a family connection and concentrated familial industry involvement, such as “the extended CoppolaSchwartzman-Cage show business family comprising [of] actors and actresses, movie producers, directors, screenwriters, and soundtrack composers” (Gorji et al. 3). Members of show business families have been shown to have better access to higher quality film projects (Gorji et al. 8) and can benefit from their families' establishment and reputation, or social capital, which provides advantageous benefits. (Gorji et al. 3). Although the specificity of differentiating ‘types’ of nepotism is not the focus, noting this element could provide a useful insight for the study. For example, if the results show an increase of nepotism from the 80's to the present then this could represent industry networks becoming more closed off to outsiders, but if most of the nepotism in the 80's was show business families while most of the recent decade's was singular family connections this could show that networks are actually more open despite the frequency of using family connections to obtain access. As well, while one relation could be coincidence, multiple relations display that they are structurally embedded in the industry.

Results

To determine if the proportion of actors with familial ties to established entertainment professionals to those without ties differs between decades, descriptive statistics and a chi-square

test of independence were used. The chi-square test of independence was chosen due to the objective to compare categorical variables, decade and nepotism status.

In Group 1, from the sampled films of 1980–1990, (N=374) 13.9% of actors were nepotism beneficiaries, compared to Group 2, from the films of 2014–2024, which was (N=360) 16.67%. A chi-square test of independence found that the difference in nepotism between decades was not statistically significant $X^2 = (1, N = 734) = 1.07, p > 0.05$.

Categories	Nepotism (1)	Non-Nepotism (0)	Total
Group 1	52	322	374
Group 2	60	300	360
Total	112	622	734

In Group 1, 94.2% of nepotism beneficiaries were related to actors, compared to 81.7% in Group 2. The next most common professions were producers and writers.

Secondary Analysis: Gender

In total from Group 1, 27.8% of all the actors were women and 30.8% of the nepotism beneficiaries were women. 15.4% of women were nepotism beneficiaries and 13.4% of men were nepotism beneficiaries.

From Group 2, 31.9% of all actors were women and 40.0% of nepotism beneficiaries were women. 20.9% of women were nepotism beneficiaries and 14.7% of men were nepotism beneficiaries.

Number of Nepotism Beneficiaries and Non-Nepotism Beneficiaries by Decade

	<u>Group 1 (1980–1990)</u>			<u>Group 2 (2014–2024)</u>		
	Nepotism (1)	Non-Nepotism (0)	Total	Nepotism (1)	Non-Nepotism (0)	Total
Female	16	88	104	24	91	115
Male	36	234	270	36	209	245
Total	52	322	374	60	300	360

Tertiary Analysis: Multiple Ties

In Group 1, 51.9% of nepotism beneficiaries had multiple family ties, which increased to 56.7% in Group 2.

Percent Distribution of Relatives of Nepotism Beneficiaries by Decade

	1 relative	2 relatives	3-5 relatives	6-9 relatives
Group 1 (1980–1990)	48.10%	28.80%	15.40%	7.70%
Group 2 (2014–2024)	43.30%	36.70%	18.30%	1.70%

Discussion

While there was ~3% increase in nepotism between decades, this amount was shown to be statistically insignificant through the chi-square test. This signifies that the rate of nepotism in the entertainment industry is consistent throughout decades. The recent popularization of the term ‘nepo baby’ appears to have little to no link with the general prevalence of nepotism, within the field of acting at least. Future research could perform a similar test for music artists or other areas of the entertainment industry to gather a wider image of the cultural landscape. Nevertheless, this study suggests that public discourse surrounding nepotism is not related to a quantifiable increase in its prevalence, rather there could be various other economic, sociological, cultural, or political factors behind mainstream interest in the topic. Potential reasons for public dissatisfaction with perceived inequality in the hiring process could be related to economic struggles, for example, with the current state of the job market people could be projecting their employment anxieties onto entertainment. As job searches have become more competitive, people could be more likely to view nepotism as a threat to their potential to find work because of the privilege it provides to

others which could make them take notice of nepotism more, especially when it comes to the media they consume. This could also relate to broader dissatisfaction with celebrities and privilege in general as cultural values celebrate individual achievements as they align with the ideals of meritocracy. Through this framework, obvious family involvement in success invalidates such achievements and when the success is so glamourized, as many celebrities are, they are often viewed as bypassing the meritocratic system. This perceived injustice could result in more discussions surrounding the topic. In terms of public opinion, social media and the internet most likely had a big impact on public awareness of the prevalence of nepotism and the spread of criticisms. In the 80's there would have been less general knowledge of familial connections to spur discussions of nepotism, and those discussions might not have gained the same traction as they have in recent years from online discourse. With general perceptions of nepotism being negative (Padgett, et al. 294; Burhan, et al. 45), it lends itself well to celebrity controversy and can be directed to criticisms of particular individuals rather than structural equality critiques. The discussion can also coincide with nostalgia, as the past is idealized in comparison to the present (Mitchell, et al. 442). Nostalgic biases can lead to clearer observations about the present prevalence while the past is viewed through 'rose coloured glasses' that ignore flaws. Further research to understand subjective views in relation to objective and quantitative data could explore the sociological environment surrounding nepotism. While acknowledging the small scale of this study, these results could indicate that the successfulness of nepotism is structural within industries because of its static persistence throughout both decades. This could be further explored by comparing nepotism prevalence in other employment areas.

Overall, the prevalence of nepotism was ~15.3% throughout both decades. While this is not an overwhelming proportion, it still demonstrates that nepotism isn't just a case of a few

individuals and is instead approximately 1 in 7. Although this study can not measure the benefits those with pre-established familial ties receive, because it does not analyze the complexities of the network system and provides a broad overview rather than specifying on a case-by-case basis whether a casting situation can be classed as nepotism, it can provide a general idea as to the extent of nepotism in the entertainment industry. Since the majority of successful actors have no pre-established ties to industry professionals, this could coincide with similar studies that suggest that actors must also demonstrate competency for the work to star in popular movies, regardless of familial ties. Nevertheless, this still falls to the critique that not having to work to create those relations and having them pre-established by family members is still a form of privilege. Additionally, it could be noted throughout the coding process that many leading actors of films had family members who had smaller appearances in said films who would most likely not have received the opportunity had it not been for their famous family member. While most of these overt nepotistic cases don't lead to overwhelming success (Gorgi et al.), they nonetheless can take roles from smaller actors. The percentage of nepotism could be interpreted as low or high depending on perceptions but data on other fields would allow for comparisons for more objective analysis.

Similar to the overall prevalence of nepotism, the number of family ties stays consistent in both decades. Nevertheless, there were some slight differences between the time periods such as with large show business families, that consist of 6 to 9 family members, which decreased from ~8% in Group 1 to ~2% in Group 2. In Group 1, the maximum amount of relatives recorded was 9 while the most from Group 2 was 7 which suggests that large show business families are less successful in the present compared to the 80's, but due to the low quantity of extended families such as these, this data is not conclusive. Another slight difference between the decades is the ~8% increase in nepotism beneficiaries with 2 relatives. While again, the change is small and could be

considered insignificant, it could also provide another possible reason for the spark in interest of ‘nepo babies’ as those with 2 relatives, usually parents, could be more likely to fall under this category. Perhaps the public notice is not in the prevalence of nepotism in general but rather in those with multiple ties because it makes the entertainment industry appear more closed off. While there is a high amount of research on perceptions of nepotism, future research could approach this same area to analyze whether the number of family ties is a component in people’s consideration.

Gender

The percentage of women overall, 27.8% and 31.9%, is consistent with wider studies that use IMDb, such as a study on Hollywood film productions between 1929 and 2010 that analysed 97,657 actors and found 30% were women (Dadlani et al. 9). This demonstrates that this much smaller scale study does contain a reasonable representation of the population in terms of gender. In both decades, women had a larger proportion within nepotism beneficiaries than in the groups as a whole. This trend also increased in Group 2. While this does show women tend to benefit from familial ties slightly more than men, the results are much less definitive compared to other studies such as Gorji et al. (9). Due to women nepotism beneficiaries being the smallest category by far and the small proportional increases, this study does not conclude that nepotism is an effective tool for women to overcome adversity within the entertainment industry. As well, due to heavier criticisms of female celebrities, women nepotism beneficiaries could endure more scrutiny than their male counterparts which could diminish the benefit of nepotism in terms of popularity. Research could seek to analyze the media’s portrayal of nepotism through a gendered lens, such as if the term ‘nepo baby’ is used more commonly against women.

Limitations

The films were chosen due to how much they grossed over their lifetime, not the amount grossed during the decade. For Group 1, this could lead to a less accurate representation of the most successful films from that time period. Due to the large sample size of 100 films, the differentiation can be assumed to be insignificant and still capture broadly the most successful films of the decade.

This study pulls from data of family members and does not account for specifics of how an actor received a job. The assumption made is that a person with familial ties to an established professional will receive privileges from said relation whether through borrowing social capital (Gorji et al. 1), using their family's contacts within the industry (Blair 152), receiving insider knowledge, being given unfair opportunities, etc. However, this assumption cannot be confirmed for all the actors who were given nepotism status since it is purely based on the relationship existing and not how the relationship was utilized. There are also possible situations that could not be accounted for. For example, while stepfamily was only counted if they were related to the actor before the actor's first film appearance, it is possible that they could have had an impact pre-official relation. As well, IMDb considers more than just first cousins under the 'cousin' category which could include some people that are distantly related, who could essentially have no effect on the other's success.

All the data used is from publicly available information, so it is possible that some industry connections are private and thus some individuals will be inaccurately marked as non-nepotistic. It is also possible that data from 1980–1990 is incomplete from fewer interviews, less family information, and limited public documents that could lead to the nepotism from this decade being underreported.

Due to the choice to use top grossing films, the study does not consider the industry as a whole and therefore the findings should be considered with caution and do not generalize the industry completely. Further research could include TV series, streaming-only productions, mid-budget films, etc. Similarly, leading roles are a subset of the industry and do not represent its entirety. Background or side actors could represent a different side of the industry, as well as writers, directors, producers, etc.

Only two decades are compared which does mean the prevalence of nepotism in the 1990s, 2000s, and 2010s could have varied. It could be a coincidence that the 1980s and most recent decade align and there might have been fluctuations in the time in between. However, it does seem unlikely that the decades would vary drastically considering the insignificant change between the 1980s and the most recent decade.

Conclusion

This study aimed to examine how the proportion of successful actors with familial ties to established entertainment professionals to those without ties compares in the 1980's to the last 10 years. The conclusion is that the prevalence of nepotism among successful actors has been static in the entertainment industry from the 1980s to the present and suggests that recent discussions surrounding the topic are due to external factors rather than based on a noticeable rise. While there are many limitations to this conclusion, this research can provide some contextual data for how nepotism presents within the entertainment industry as well as introduce a discussion on how the media and public's view of nepotism is disconnected from objective measurement. Nepotism and the extent to which it disadvantages others, the process of networking, and the impact of reputation on casting choices are all complex sociological issues, nevertheless, this study aims to provide

some quantitative figure for the prevalence of pre-established familial ties to entertainment professionals among successful actors.

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